

Selection of Effective Factors in Estimating of Costumers Respond to Mobile Advertising by Using AHP

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Abstract: This paper presents an application of the analytic hierarchy process used to selection of effective factors in estimating of costumers' respond to mobile advertising and then investigates the most successful factors form of mobile communication; short message services (SMS). This method adapts a multi-criteria approach that can be used for analysis and comparison of mobile advertising. Four criteria were used for evaluating mobile advertising: Information services, Entertainment, Coupons, Location base services. For each, a matrix of pair wise comparisons between factors influence was evaluated. Finley the aim of this investigate is to gain a better understanding of how companies use mobile advertising in doing business.

Keywords: : Mobile Advertising; E Advertising; Personalization; Analytic Hierarchy Process; Short Message Services (SMS); Successful Factors

1 Introduction

With a growth and progress in electronic business, especially in cellular phones, mobile advertisement seems to be successful when elements which are effective on customer's attitude in electronic and wireless situation are to be well-understood and necessary actions shall be done in this case. While several elements are effective on customer's attitude owe can mention to personal values and inner believes customer's characteristics and also technological and media elements and even strategies which companies take up and finally

put them in to analysis.

Recently a great attention has been veered toward the efficacy of mobile advertisement in cellular phones from scholars and experts. This is due to the peculiarity of cellular phone which makes it different from other media, for instance we can mention to personalization of advertisement.

Online advertising (ad) is a form of promotion that uses the Internet and World Wide Web for the express purpose of delivering marketing messages to attract customers [3].

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2 Literature review

2.1 Mobile advertising

Short message services (SMS) have become a new technological buzzword in transmitting business to customer messages to such wireless devices as cellular telephones, pagers, and personal data assistants. Many brands and media companies include text message numbers in their advertisements to enable interested consumers to obtain more information [4]. Mobile marketing uses interactive wireless media to deliver personalized time- and location-sensitive information promoting goods, services, and ideas, thereby generating value for all stakeholders [2]. Studying interactive mobile services such as SMS and MMS suggests drawing upon theories in marketing, consumer behavior, psychology and adoption to investigate their organizational and personal use [4].

Mobile advertising is predicted to be an important source of revenue for mobile operators in the future [9] and has been identified as one of the most promising potential business areas. For instance, in comparison with much advertising in traditional media, mobile Advertisements can be customized to better suit a consumer's needs and improve client relationship [1]. Examples of mobile advertising methods include mobile banners, alerts, and proximity-triggered advertisements [6].

2.2 The AHP

The AHP is one the extensively used multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods. The AHP has been applied to a wide variety of decisions including car purchasing, IS project selection [8], and IS success [5].

The AHP is aimed at integrating different measures in to a signal overall score for ranking decision alternative. Its main characteristic is that it is based on pair wise comparison judgments.

In this paper, we discuss one representative the relationship between the effective factors in success the marketing companies and also influence the way the consumer reacts to mobile advertising.

3 Alternatives

3.1 Personalization

Marketers can personalize text messages based on the consumers local time, location, and preferences, directions to the nearest vegetarian restaurant open at the time of request. A person may use a mobile device to receive information but also for a purpose of personal entertainment, it mean if any matter (mobile SMS/Advertising) will disturb his personal entertainment then he will never like to disclose his personal information [10].

3.2 Credibility

The credibility of the mobile applications is what makes their uses frequent. If the user experienced a problem during the transaction or mobile advertising, it is certain that it will not use the mobile applications once more [7].

3.3 Consumer permission

Corporate advertising often serve as the primary point of contact, asking consumers for permission to receive SMS and According to all the experts, advertisers should have permission and convince consumers to opt in before sending advertisements [1].

3.4 Consumer control

There is a trade-off between personalization and consumer control. Gathering data required for tailoring messages raises privacy concerns. Corporate policies must consider legalities such as electronic signatures, electronic contracts, and conditions for sending SMS messages [1].

Figure 1: Hierarchical model for selection of effective factors

4 A case study using AHP

4.1 Applying the AHP method

4.1.1 Breaking down the problem

The first step was to develop a hierarchical structure of the problem. This classifies the goal and all decision criteria and variables into three major levels, as depicted in Figure 1. The highest level of the hierarchy is the overall goal: to select the best influence factors mobile advertisement. Level 2 represents the criteria that companies offer the services for their customers. Level 3 contains the decision alternatives that in mobile ads we consider the types of proposed solutions which are important to users.

4.1.2 Comparative judgments to establish priorities

After calculating the weight of the effective elements in mobile ads in relation to the total designated criteria, we should determine the weight of the criteria. In other words, the quota of each criterion in determining the best effective element must be identified. To do this we need to compare the criteria in pairs. For example, in order to determine the relative importance of the four major criteria, a 4 × 4 matrix was formed. Expert Choice provided ratings to facilitate comparison, these then needed to be incorporated into the decision making process. After inputting the criteria and their importance into Expert Choice, the priorities from each set of judgments were found.

4.2 Discussion of results

In the previous section the weight of the criteria with regard to the purpose and also the weight of the alternatives with regard to the criteria were determined. Now, the way relative weights are combined for evaluating the final weights to choose and prioritize the best elements will be explained in Fig2. Since the rate of compatibility is less than 0.1, it can be concluded that the group decision has an acceptable compatibility. Therefore, the obtained results consist of personalizing messages in the first rank with the final weight of 0.484, message credit with the weight of 0.310 in the second rank. Sending message in an appointed time with the weight of 0.118 in the third rank, and the right of message reception on the part of the user with the weight of 0.089 in the final rank.

5 Conclusion

Online advertising is a new service in the marketing industry. An AHP-based methodology was designed and applied and has proven its potential in helping decision-makers in supporting in order to specify and prioritize elements that are effective on mobile business processes in cellular phone user, in has paid attention to find out the relation between attitude and effective element in comparison with mobile advertisement in cellular phones. Finally we were show the operational process of hierarchical analysis on the mobile advertisement.

Figure 2: Synthesis for Select best influence factors

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